

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D5.5 – Access and User Management System for Life Science – the implementation and usage report

WP5 – User management and access services

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Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the work done in implementing an access and user management system for the European life science research infrastructures during the EOCS-Life project. The Life Science AAI (Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure), branded for users as the Life Science Login, provides a way to coordinate how user identity and access is managed in research services and data in the (community-specific) federated Infrastructure. The service has been managed by the life sciences community and operated by Masaryk University with the e-infrastructures, specifically GEANT and EGI, during the project. This model of operation continues after the project concludes.

The work package has followed the updated Life Science AAI blueprint (Deliverable D5.4) to implement the AAI service from technical, policy and legal perspectives. The Life Science AAI is fully implemented and in production since 11th of April 2022. To support the usage of the service the launch activity has been done in parallel with a merge of the AAI operated by ELIXIR, followed by the migration of BBMRI-ERIC AAI into the Life Science AAI. For the duration of the project, the WP has also been executing work to integrate other infrastructures by integrating (at least partially) and preparing the environment for a full-scale consolidation of the infrastructures into the Life Science AAI.

The service statistics, including active user accounts, number of services, number of logins, service availability, etc, will be described in Chapter 6 - Usage report.

This deliverable describes the technical architecture of the Life Science AAI and explains how implementation and delivery of the service were coordinated between EOCS-Life partners and the e-infrastructures. The deliverable includes current progress on policy work, which is crucial for the operations of the service. The current state of the service is described as well as processes developed as part of the operations, including processes for registration services or processes for helpdesk coordination between EOCS-Life partners and e-infrastructures. The deliverable also covers updates on the access management system ARIA, including the steps for integration with Life Science AAI.

To illustrate the intention and results of the project, key performance indicators are summarised in the table below. The success of establishing the Life Science AAI is demonstrated by three key usage indicators: the number of active accounts, number of Relying Parties utilising the AAI functionality and number of logins per month.

Date	LS IDs registered	Registered RPs (prod. / test env.)	Logins per month
04/2022 (Launch date)	~ 9000	~ 150 / 160	~ 6000
06/2023 (D5.5 submission)	14 213	165 / 189	13123

Project objectives

In this deliverable we describe how EOSC-Life WP5 has contributed to the following objectives:

- a. To specify/define a convergent access and user management system to enable multi-RI applications and workflows that build on existing approaches (LS AAI, ARIA, Negotiator service, etc.) and support access to sensitive data with their specific requirements
- b. To implement federated life science authentication and authorization infrastructure (AAI) and access proposal/control system supporting access through different user entry points, managing user life cycle and controlling and providing fine-grained access control to the resources;

Detailed report on the deliverable

1. Background

The need to authenticate researchers and manage their access rights is common to many research infrastructures. Research infrastructures need to protect access to confidential information (such as samples from human patients or information about ongoing or proposed research projects) or expensive resources (such as sophisticated instruments or computing capacity). This requires sufficient information about who the users are (identity proofing and user authentication), whom they are representing (affiliation with a home organisation) and what resources they can access (authorisation). These services are called authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI). For more information on the AAI terms, concepts and paradigms, refer to section 1 of CORBEL D6.5 [CORB19].

Providing services for researcher authentication and authorisation fits well with the research infrastructures' mission to support researchers' work. Research infrastructures are permanent entities facilitating research projects in collaboration with the research communities. They are well-connected in their domain and able to understand the common needs of their user communities. On the other hand, AAI is not a core business for research infrastructures and so they need to collaborate in the research and education sector with other actors (such as e-infrastructures) who have a long history of developing the underlying AAI technologies and services.

As a result of the past CORBEL WP5 and AARC2 projects, EOSC-Life WP5 was chartered to define and implement Life Science AAI. In September 2019, deliverable D5.1 presented the blueprint of the Life Science AAI, including its technical and non-technical requirements. This deliverable describes the project's progress towards implementing the blueprint and launching a Life Science AAI service. This work has been gradually updated and reported in further deliverables D5.3 in March 2021 and D5.4 in June 2022. Updated deliverables are revisions of the previous deliverables and contain updates of the relevant sections including newly gathered requirements.

Some BMS RIs have operated their RI-wide AAI services for several years, including BBMRI-ERIC AAI and ELIXIR AAI. While those AAI services have been important for understanding the BMS

community's needs on AAI, the eventual goal of Life Science AAI has been to enable their migration to the Life Science AAI during the EOSC-Life project. Migration of the existing AAI to Life Science AAI is covered in deliverables D5.3 and D5.4.

2. Life Science AAI Service Ecosystem

Life Science AAI is the common Authentication and Authorisation service portfolio for the research infrastructures participating in the EOSC-Life project and beyond. The Life Science AAI ecosystem covers not only the technical part but also policies and operations. The goal has been to deliver a fully functional ecosystem which might be used by users from all around the world without any technical or legal barriers.

The ecosystem consists of services/components operated by biological and medical research infrastructures, services/components provided by e-infrastructures and possibly other parts provided by third parties. This chapter describes the architecture, how the service ecosystem is coordinated and applicable policies.

2.1 Service coordination

Life Science AAI is a service owned by the Life Science community, as represented by WP5 for the duration of the EOSC-Life project. In the adopted deployment model, e-infrastructures (EGI and GEANT) are operating some of the key technical components of the Life Science AAI.

The figure below outlines three layers:

- **Life Science AAI operators** are the e-infrastructures running the technical components of the Life Science AAI.
- **Life Science AAI coordination** is the way for the Life Science community to organise the management and coordination of the Life Science AAI service.
- **Services relying on the Life Science AAI** are the customers of the Life Science AAI; the Life Science AAI exists to solve their needs on authentication and authorisation of the LS researchers. Services may be managed by the research infrastructures, organisations (such as universities or research institutes) affiliated with the research infrastructures, e-infrastructures or companies (such as commercial cloud providers). It is assumed that the relying services do not participate directly in the coordination of the Life Science AAI.

The EOSC-Life WP5 has been the coordination function that drives the Life Science AAI-related issues and discussion within the LS community and channels it to the Life Science AAI operators. Similarly, the Life Science AAI operators have coordinated the operations of the Life Science AAI. Although informal communication took place in several channels, the formal dialogue (including potential agreements) between the Life Science AAI coordination and operation has been taking place between the two coordination functions.

The coordination has been taking place in two working groups;

- the technical deployment work has been coordinated by the Life Science AAI Technical working group.
- the policy and legal framework for Life Science AAI has been coordinated by the Life Science AAI Policy working group.

For the long-time sustainability of the Life Science AAI, it is necessary to identify the permanent entities that are responsible for organising the coordination functionality. However, presenting the long-term sustainable model for the Life Science AAI service is not in the scope of this deliverable.

2.2 Overall technical architecture

A proof of concept for the architecture for Life Science AAI was implemented during a pilot in collaboration with CORBEL WP5 and the AARC2 project in 2018. In September 2019, EOSC-Life WP5 delivered (Deliverable D5.1) an updated version of the technical requirements along with a new document describing the operational requirements and the available budget for the service. Even though the initial Proof of concept architecture met most of the technical requirements, it became evident that the operational cost of the architecture would significantly exceed the available budget.

Taking these into account, the e-infrastructures revisited the original architecture and produced a simplified, streamlined update focusing on delivering the required functional and operational requirements within the budget constraints of EOSC-Life. The technical architecture that has been deployed and is presented here is based on the streamlined model. Gradually, as the project proceeded, the Life Science community has been expressing further needs that needed to be addressed. These items have been described in the updates of the blueprint architecture represented by deliverables D5.3 and D5.4.

The diagram below illustrates the main components of Life Science AAI and its key integrations. A user logs in using an external identity provider, such as their home university or research institution logins (via the eduGAIN inter-federation service operated by GEANT) or community or commercial alternatives (such as ORCID or Google). To extend the base of researchers who can authenticate using the infrastructure and do not have access or do not want to use the mentioned identity providers, an alternative locally managed Identity Provider offering to register a local username and password credentials has been introduced. After the authentication using the identity provider is completed, the Life Science AAI gathers the logged-in user’s extra attributes from its internal sources and presents them to the services relying on Life Science AAI as illustrated in the upper part of the diagram. Such relying services can be instruments (producing data for research purposes), data archives (managing data for secondary use), computing and cloud services (enabling researchers to compute on data) and various collaborative tools that support researchers’ interaction (such as wikis, content management systems, mailing lists or e-learning environments).

The internal architecture of Life Science AAI is composed of two main logical components: the identity management (IdM) system and the access management (AM) system. The key component of the access management is the IdP/SP Proxy component whose purpose is to handle user authentication for the services connected to Life Science AAI. The proxy is an adapter between the external identity providers and the end services and in that role can do protocol and attribute

translation when required by their specific needs. This opens the possibility for handling compatibility issues in a distributed environment where different actors have adopted heterogeneous technical approaches. The proxy is a critical component of the AAI because it handles all authentication transactions, therefore any outage of the proxy will have an impact on users.

Even though the main functionality of the proxy is mostly technical and therefore transparent for the users, the proxy is enhanced with other features realised as modules or separate components. The proxy can interrupt the user flow and interact with them. A typical use case is to redirect new users to a registration, another example might be to check if the user is authorised to use the service which they are trying to access. If the user doesn't fulfil all conditions, the proxy can offer a solution in the form of immediate action (e.g. ask the user logged-in to accept the necessary acceptable usage policy) or redirect users to documentation or to a page where they can request access.

The proxy solely handles the whole authentication flow of the users, therefore it is a logical place where stronger forms of authentication might be enforced. In some cases, the Proxy can know if the stronger authentication method (e.g. multifactor authentication, MFA) was used by an upstream identity provider and react accordingly. For example, if the service which a user is trying to access requires strong authentication and it was not done by the external identity provider, the proxy can force users to perform multi-factor authentication provided by Life Science AAI. The proxy can even signal to the external identity provider that multifactor authentication is required, so the external identity provider can act accordingly.

The proxy is tightly integrated with the second main component which is the identity management system that manages all data related to the users and their identity, including their attributes. It also manages information required for authorisation decisions, such as groups, membership, roles or entitlements. The identity management system is designed to store data obtained from various sources. The primary sources are the users' external identity providers which may be authoritative sources for their role and affiliation in their home organisation. Using the APIs of the identity management system, data can be synchronised and stored also from other systems, such as REMS (Resource Entitlement Management System), ARIA, BBMRI Directory and BBMRI Negotiator.

The identity management system provides a user interface where delegated managers can manage their users, organise them in groups and add access rights to them. User application management is also available which enables managers to define registration flows to individual groups including user life cycle in the groups. Users without a manager role can access their user profile to update their contact information, linked identities, the local password for authentication, and other credentials (e.g. public keys for SSH secure shell access).

The identity management system can provision and deprovision user data or authorisation rules for other services. This enables Life Science AAI to cater for services where users don't sign in directly (e.g. management of mailing lists) or services which need to be notified promptly about user status changes, even without direct user interactions (e.g. stopping cloud machines when the user is no longer authorised to use them).

The provisioning mechanisms of both IdM and AM components are effectively a procedure for communicating the user data to the relying services to allow them to perform their own identification and authorisation tasks. As the procedure deals with personal data, this fact needs to be communicated to the end users. Life Science AAI has implemented a consent mechanism to enforce users' acknowledgment if such an action is required. Users are allowed to allow or decline the information transfer. Without explicitly granting the consent the service will receive no data about the user. To provide a better user experience of the implemented functionality they can also

opt for a mode where the Life Science AAI will not inform them about the fact anymore for some time unless this changes or the period for which the consent has been granted has expired. Accompanying this functionality is the procedure for managing the granted consents, via which holders of the Life Science ID can review the consents they have granted and actively revoke them.

Overall, the Life Science AAI architecture is designed to be modular. There are the aforementioned two main logical components which act as a foundation for the other components and integrations. The proxy handles anything related to user authentication flow, including connected external identity providers and the relying services. The identity management system can be used as a source or for storage of data, and for integration via the provisioning mechanism.

The proxy is based on the SATOSA¹ product and the identity management system is based on the Perun² product. Both components are operated by e-infrastructures. For providing additional functionality several other microservices have been introduced and deployed into the architecture in either direct modules integrated into these primary components, or as standalone services integrated via other mechanisms (like via API). Such an example is a GA4GH Passports and Visas broker to facilitate the support of GA4GH³ Passport and Visas standards. Another example is the Multi-Factor Authentication component based on the privacyIDEA⁴ product.

2.3 User registration and account linking

To start using Life Science AAI, a user needs to register a Life Science ID and commit to the Life Science AAI Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP). Registration of the Life Science ID is open to anyone. The goal is to eliminate all barriers for users which might complicate the usage of Life Science AAI. Users are encouraged to use their existing digital identities in the external identity providers to apply for the Life Science ID. Most academic users can use the digital identity provided by their home institution and made accessible through the academic identity federation eduGAIN. That is bringing comfort for users who don't need to manage another set of credentials but can use their regular credentials that they are using daily in the home institution. That also covers typical problems with lost credentials and their recovery. Users can leverage their local support in their institution, which is more comfortable than any possible remote support by the Life Science AAI operators. Moreover, if the home identity provider supports single sign-on, it will also cover authentication to Life Science AAI.

An alternative to using home institution identity providers is using community or commercial identity providers like ORCID, Google, LinkedIn or Apple. Those identity providers offer similar comfort to academic ones and are available for the majority of users, but are primarily serving as the fallback options due to their lack of ability to express e.g. affiliation with the home organisation. They would typically only enable a user to access public data. As a last resort, a Life Science local username and password identity provider is available, which enables users to create a new account with new credentials and use it as authentication to their Life Science ID. This solution might be suitable for users who cannot use other options or who prefer to have a local account only for Life Science AAI.

¹ <https://github.com/IdentityPython/SATOSA>

² <https://perun-aa.org/>

³ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

⁴ <https://www.privacyidea.org/>

Utilising an external identity provider requires solving the possibility of one user having several options of external identity providers available. The Life Science AAI allows a user to link multiple external identities to a single Life Science ID. To link additional identity a user has to prove that they can authenticate with a new one as well as the one which is already linked. After the linking, the user can use any of the linked identities to authenticate to their Life Science ID. Account linking might be automatically offered during registration of a new account when systems discover accounts with the same or similar properties, e.g. an account using the same email address. In that case, users can decide to only link a new identity instead of creating a new account.

Account linking is helpful when users are migrating from one institution to another, which would often mean they will use the option to use the identity provider from the previous institution, but they can also use the one from the new institution once linked. Following the same principle, users might link their social identity to have a backup way to access their Life Science ID in case they won't be able to use the primary authentication method. The last benefit of account linking is user comfort for users who are regularly using multiple authentication methods. Thanks to linked accounts users can choose any linked account to authenticate which will always lead to the same result.

Due to the increasing requirements on protecting the user accounts both from users' and relying services' perspectives the Life Science AAI introduced a pilot implementation of a Multi-Factor authentication in a distributed research infrastructure environment. The primary idea is to leverage the existing solutions provided by identity providers for performing the authentication using multiple factors in an environment already familiar to the users and so reduce complexity. To facilitate the missing functionality in a particular home organisation identity provider, users can use other linked external identities which might support the process. Alternatively, as an ultimate fallback solution, the infrastructure provides a last-resort component where users can associate secondary factor(s) with their Life Science ID.

2.4 Implementation progress

Implementation of Life Science AAI started in September 2019, after the publication of Deliverable D5.1. For the internal management and prioritisation of the implementation work, the features presented in D5.1 were deployed in three phases called "bumps". Those formed the basis for monitoring the progress of the deployment. The deployment of the functionality began in 2019, primarily as a testbed for the integration of the identified components. The Life Science AAI has been launched as a public service to any individual coming from the Life Sciences research cluster on the 11th of April 2022. At the same moment, ELIXIR AAI has been migrated resulting in a full merge into the launched service. Following that, on the 9th of May 2023 the BBMRI AAI has been migrated in the same fashion. Also, the ARIA system has been integrated, but only in using the Life Science AAI as one of the authentication methods. However, the service is now able to consume user authentication from the Life Science AAI which results in interoperability with Life Science AAI-enabled relying parties.

The first "bump" had the theme "**make it start**" and covered the very necessary functionality; no viable Life Science AAI service could be offered without all of these features. It covered:

- Deployment of key components, including the proxy identity provider (SATOSA) and the Identity Management service (Perun).
- Identity Provider Discovery service (for an end user to select their authentication provider) and its usability evaluation.

- Proxy identity provider registration to eduGAIN (to enable end users to log in with their Home organisation identities) and selected commercial and community authentication providers (such as ORCID and Google).
- Flow for registering new users and populating their required attributes, including the users' approval of the Acceptable Usage Policy of Life Science AAI.
- Flow for the registered users to link and unlink their Life Science ID to more identity providers.
- Endpoints (SAML 2.0 and OpenID Connect) to which the relying services can integrate to authenticate users and receive their attributes.
- Service to monitor the availability of the Life Science AAI components.
- Redundant setup, where the critical components of the Life Science AAI are run in at least two instances.

The second “bump” had the theme **“let relying parties and users in”** and covered those features that build on top of the first bump and make it convenient for relying services and users to start using Life Science AAI. It covered:

- Migration plan for ELIXIR AAI, BBMRI AAI and ARIA.
- Test environment where developers can test their service integration with Life Science AAI before exposing it to production use.
- Life Science local username and password (previously Life Science Hostel) Identity Provider where those end users can create an account (with username and password) whose home organisation is not integrated to eduGAIN and who don't want to use the available community or commercial alternatives (like ORCID and Google) for login.
- Automated tools and flows for relying service administrators to register and manage their services in Life Science AAI.
- Public statistics and catalogue pages of the relying services registered to Life Science AAI and the number of logins by end users into these services using the Life Science AAI.

The third “bump” had the label **“complete the functionality”**. It covered:

- Service accounts that are needed when servers or machine accounts need to communicate with Life Science AAI or with each other.
- Multi-Factor Authentication for relying services with higher security requirements and related framework to communicate achieved assurance levels to downstream services.
- Manual management of affiliation information for users from those home organisations that cannot deliver the information programmatically (using the eduPersonAffiliation attribute delivered by the Identity Provider).
- Making available other attributes relevant for relying services, such as Home research infrastructure, Home country, and Researcher status.
- Delivery of permissions to access sensitive human data, following the emerging Passport specification from the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health.
- Active role selection, enabling a user with multiple roles (e.g. project memberships, affiliation) to select one for use in the current session.
- Access control is enforced in the proxy, enabling a relying service to request the Proxy Identity Provider deny access for users who don't qualify for the access policy (e.g. group membership) as configured for the relying service.
- Credential translation, enabling an end user to receive an X.509 certificate if required for accessing a particular relying service.
- Complex protocol flows, such as the device code flow of OpenID Connect that enables e.g. Life Science AAI login with SSH Secure Shell.

- Service level reporting from e-infrastructures to the Life Science community.

New requirements and clarifications to existing requirements have been presented in the deliverables D5.3 and D5.4, which are incremental updates of the D5.1 “Access and User Management System for Life Science – The Blueprint”. These covered:

- Area: Identity and identifiers
 - Life Science ID
 - User identifiers
 - Cardinality of identities
- Area: Registering with and authenticating to Life Science AAI
 - Registering a Life Science ID
 - Supported Authentication providers and their discovery
 - Hostel Identity Provider
 - Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP)
 - Account linking for Life Science user IDs
 - Account management for Life Science service IDs
 - Assurance framework
 - Step-up authentication
- Area: Attributes and authorisation
 - Home Organisation Affiliation(s) of a user
 - Home Organisation properties
 - Researcher status and attestations
 - GA4GH Passports
 - Groups
 - Dataset authorisation
 - Resource capabilities
 - Other attributes
 - Life Science ID user profile panel
- Area: Access control
 - Active role selection
 - Access control enforcement during login
 - Life Science AAI Test environment
- Area: Technical interfaces
 - Federated login and attribute release
 - Attribute retrieval from external sources
 - Credential translation
 - User synchronisation
 - Provisioning
- Area: Logging, statistics and data retention
- Area: Information security
- Area: Usability
 - Ease of use
 - Usability expert review
 - Consistency
- Area: Capacity
- Area: Accessibility & Compatibility

2.5 Life Science AAI Policy

This section gives a high-level overview of the policy environment of Life Science AAI, including GDPR considerations, the contractual relations with external parties and the terms for the end users.

The Life Science AAI intends to be a permanent service with a sustainable governance and funding model that has been developed as a part of the EOSC-Life project. This is the subject of ongoing discussions with all the partners so will not be further specified in this document.

2.5.1 Overview and assumptions

The diagram above gives a high-level view of the flow of information (personal data) that takes place when a researcher from an identity provider (such as their home university) logs in to a relying service via the Life Science AAI. The diagram highlights:

- Typical attributes that an identity provider may release to Life Science AAI and the Life Science AAI may release to a relying service.
- That some external identity providers and relying parties are established outside the European Economic Area.
- That some components of the Life Science AAI are operated by e-infrastructures as contractors of the Life Science community.

In the development of the policy, the following assumptions related to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) have been made and have been further reflected in the approach in several policy documents:

- The external identity providers, Life Science Community and Relying parties (that manage the relying services) are all independent data controllers.
- During the project, Life Science Community has been represented by Masaryk University which acts as the Life Science AAI data controller. The situation will remain the same after the project completes.

- E-infrastructures (GEANT and EGI) are data processors, processing personal data on behalf of the Life Science community.
- All data released by Life Science AAI qualifies as personal data. No special categories of personal data are processed in Life Sciences AAI.
- The legal grounds of personal data processing is a contract.

2.5.2 Virtual Organisations

Inside the Life Science AAI, research infrastructures and other communities may have their own smaller containers called “Virtual Organisations” (VO) which include their pool of users and relying services that are not necessarily exposed to other VOs. A VO may

- Introduce additional policies to users and relying services and impose its approval criteria for them.
- Manage extra user attributes that are not visible to other VOs.
- Have nominated staff that have enhanced privileges to view and manage users and relying services in the VO.

By default, all users and relying services belong to the catch-all VO “lifescience”, representing the Life Science community as a whole. In the case of special needs, as mentioned before, each sub-community may be represented by a separate VO object, which provides the community with the mentioned tooling. However, to avoid fragmentation and unnecessary obstacles for researchers consuming services from multiple research infrastructures, relying services are encouraged to make use of the catch-all VO to the extent possible.

The initially implemented model technically puts the catch-all VO and the community VOs on the same level, with mechanisms of inclusion to express the fact that the community is a part of the life science community. In the evolution of the service, it is expected that the catch-all VO and separate VOs will be transformed into a hierarchical structure, where the catch-all VO will be the root of the tree hierarchy. Separate VOs will then form branches of the tree with the possibility that some structural units from the separate VO can be also used in the context of catch-all VO, e.g. for defining authorisation rules.

In this model the data controller of the Life Science AAI is likely to be the data controller of the VOs.

2.5.3 Contractual relations

This section highlights the contractual relationships the Life Science community (the Life Science AAI’s data controller) has with external parties and end users. The relationships are illustrated in the diagram and further described below.

Life Science AAI's relation with end users are defined in the following policy documents:

- **The Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP)** for end users describes what Life Science AAI expects from an end user (don't share your credentials, don't do anything unlawful, etc). It also links to the Life Science AAI's privacy notice. (Appendix A.1)
- **The Privacy Notice (PN) and Cookie policy** for end users of Life Science AAI to communicate to the end users in plain language what processing will be done on their personal data including the basis for the processing, their rights as Data Subjects, and GDPR contact points for their requests, complaints or enquiries. (Appendix A.2)

Life Science AAI's relation with other entities are described in the following contractual documents

- External identity providers' **Terms of Use** cover the conditions under which the identity providers let Life Science AAI authenticate researchers and receive some of their attributes. These terms are typically set by the identity providers and cannot be negotiated (therefore they are not further discussed in this document). They normally exclude liability and cover requirements for data protection. Some terms (e.g. GEANT Data Protection Code of Conduct and REFEDS Research and Scholarship) also influence the relying services of the Life Science AAI.
- Life Science AAI's **Terms of Use for the relying parties** cover the obligations and rights between the Life Science AAI and the relying parties, including Life Science AAI's liability for service malfunction and quality as well as the relying parties' data protection obligations. (Appendix A.3)
- Some relying services of Life Science AAI may be established outside EU/EEA and countries which meet data protection adequacy requirements. GDPR expects the Life Science community to have **appropriate safeguards** for those transfers of personal data (e.g. EC model contracts) in place.
- E-infrastructures (GEANT, EGI) are assumed to operate the technical core components of the Life Science AAI on behalf of the Life Science community. The e-infrastructures are data processors for the Life Science community and the Life Science AAI data controller has got a **data processing agreement** with them.

Furthermore, Life Science AAI has some common policies which apply to several actors:

To whom does the policy apply	Relying Parties	Virtual Organisations	Life Science AAI controller (and operator)
Service Operations security policy	X	X	X
Incident response procedures	X		X
Policy for processing personal data	X	X	X
Membership management policy		X	

- **Service operations security policy** introduces the baseline expectations for operational information security that all need to comply with. (Appendix A.4)
- **Incident response procedures** document introduces step-by-step instructions for the security contact of the Life Science AAI and relying service in case of an information security incident. (Appendix A.5)
- **Policy for processing personal data** defines the principles that must be followed in processing an end user's personal data. (Appendix A.6)
- **Membership management policy** defines the obligations of the research infrastructures or other communities who choose to introduce and manage a VO of their own. (Appendix A.7)

2.5.4 Related policy work

Several components of the Life Science AAI policy are based on the Policy Development Kit (PDK)⁵ prepared and published by the AARC project. To make the policy fit the needs of the Life Science community, some key adjustments are listed below:

- Redesigning the “infrastructure” concept. In the PDK, infrastructure covers not just the AAI but also “the IT hardware, software, networks, data, facilities, processes and any other elements that together are required to develop, test, deliver, monitor, control or support services” which are, in turn, defined as “components fulfilling a need of the users, such as computing, storage, networking or software systems.” This wide definition of infrastructure goes beyond the mandate of the Life Science AAI which focuses only on the AAI service.
- Following the narrower definition of the AAI service, the Top level policy was removed from the set of policies. As the Life Science AAI service is operated by Masaryk University, a document defining Masaryk University's internal managerial responsibilities was not directly relevant.

2.6 User Experience Analysis

When building the AAI for the life sciences community it is essential to meet the expectations of its users through the mechanisms by which they log in. While the power of a multi-federated authentication platform is very useful for service operators and for authorization attributes and

⁵ <https://aarc-project.eu/policies/policy-development-kit/>

identity vetting, the average user ‘simply wants to log in’. Such a frictionless authentication flow is essential for the success of the platform. An extensive user experience analysis has been performed building on the work done in the REFEDS community regarding proposed interfaces for authentication.

The work began by identifying the key objectives of Life Science AAI and defining the aims it wanted to achieve through the use of Life Science AAI. It was key to define what the Life Science AAI user communities will look like and identify some ‘personas’ that represent those user groups. WP has assessed the existing interface that was available in the ELIXIR AAI as a starting point for how the Life Science AAI may look when it moves to production and identified key problems and objectives to improve it. Competitor analysis was also performed using some of the key authentication technologies that people are used to using day-to-day. ORCID, Microsoft 365, Google, LinkedIn, OneLogin and Facebook were all assessed. This was driven by a strong belief that whilst the platform is research-focused, users should not have to re-learn new mechanisms for authenticating to these tools that they already know through their experience of other tools in everyday use.

Problem

- Users are given too many login options (On the login page)
- People have multiple institutional login accounts along with social accounts, having to log in to various services with different accounts

Objectives

- Drive adoption of institutional logins for identity vetting purposes
- Streamline onboarding, offboarding and general usability
- Simplify login page and consolidate multiple login options
- Create a trusted brand that scientists and students will adopt

User stories are a method of capturing things that a user may want to do when using a piece of software. The primary input has been the identification of user stories for all of the aspects of login for Life Science AAI and aligne these to one or more of the personas. From these user stories, objectives and existing UIs for ELIXIR AAI a number of wireframe prototypes for a new login system have been produced. This prototype focused on users entering an email address as the primary step and being guided through the authentication workflows as a result.

Prototype screens were implemented as a click-through prototype and then several users were invited to perform a user test. A tool called Lookback has been used to perform these user tests. The user was given a scenario based on the user stories identified earlier in the process and key tasks to perform relating to the authentication flows. Lookback software allowed recording both the user’s face and voice along with their browser window as they were going through the tasks. Users were encouraged to talk through their experience as they used the prototype and fed back any comments about the process as they went through it. Based on this the team has identified common pain points and performed a quantitative analysis of the results while ensuring the design was not being shifted based on the individual preferences of the respondents. Having performed a user test the work has been further iterated on the UIs which were implemented.

Before the launch of the Life Science AAI to production in April 2022, the need to brand the service in a more user-explanatory way has been identified. Therefore, from the user's perspective, the service is referred to as the Life Science Login. This makes it easy to communicate the service purpose to the users. Also, the UI of the components was further adjusted based on a discussion with the BBMRI User Experience (UX) experts’ group:

- UI proposal for the LS local account (LS Hostel) - process and UI for the registration of local LS account and user login via this option. The following scenarios were covered:
 - Discovery page - the place where users select this option to log in
 - Login flow
 - Registration flow
 - Set/Reset password for the user and forgotten password flows
- UI proposal for the Extended list of IdPs in the Discovery page
- UI proposal for the Previously selected IdP
- UI proposal for the Consent for attribute release UI

From Autumn 2022 an internal UX group consisting of the members of several communities actively using the Life Science AAI has been established. It gathered inputs from the communities over several months concerning the usage of the Life Science AAI.

The following findings were identified and fixes were defined:

- Removing the LS Register button - this function is redundant. Registration is often part of the Login flow and it is confusing to users when to use which button (Login vs. Register).
 - Fix: Guidelines for users and service providers were adjusted accordingly.
 - Fix: Registration button usage has been discouraged
- Hostel (Local account) - requires functionality to remind users of a forgotten username and a subsequent flow to reset the forgotten password.
 - Fix: password reset functionality provided
 - Fix: username reminder functionality provided (in progress)
- Missing variants and formats of the Life Science AAI logos (and other branding components) which can be used on different backgrounds and situations:
 - Fix: Provided more different logo formats and variants for Service providers. Published on the Life Science AAI webpage (more in progress)
- Redirecting issues: redirecting back to the relying service after completing the registration during the login flow does not always work. This happens more frequently for some Identity Providers which can be measured and fed back.
 - Fix: Instructions in FAQ for both users and service providers were published.
 - Fix: improvements in the registration handling component
- Adjustments of documentation, guidelines and FAQ for users and service providers to better match real use cases and typical issues.
 - Fix: new version of the Life Science AAI⁶ webpage was published in April 2023 based on these comments. The new version is structured differently to better align with more intuitive navigation on pages. Guidelines and documentation were updated, instructions video added, and FAQ updated. Life Science AAI web updates will be required on a regular basis even after the project end.

Continuous monitoring and adjustments will be required over time with ongoing use of the service:

- adjustment of the Discovery Page (registration flow, used Identity Provider management panel, linking of unrecognised identity to an existing LS ID, ...)
- logo adjustments to correspond with the actual needs, re-wording and adjustments of non-intuitive flows, provision of error messages with more details

⁶ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/>

Together with the Euro-BioImaging community, in May 2023 a simple usability test was executed. About 20 testers followed a scenario of registering the LS ID as a new user. Based on the test results several issues have been identified (some specific to the Euro-BioImaging community). Also, some common issues which require more complex solutions and need follow-up actions from a long-term perspective have been identified:

- Some Identity Providers do not comply with eduGAIN rules despite being registered as inter-federation members.
- Services using SAML protocol can face some issues where the recommendation is to switch to OIDC or update their underlying software as needed to support the protocol.

An agreement has been made to continue with usability tests in future and to include a wider audience as well as to prepare a methodology for Life Science AAI service quality measurements for end users and services. These activities will follow after the end of the project. Before the project end, there is still a plan for the first round of the basic questionnaire. Findings coming from the analysis of survey results will help with the continuous improvements of the user experience. More information about the survey can be found in Chapter 8.1.4 - User Experience continuous improvements.

Up-to-date guidelines for the users and relevant process description can be found on the Life Science AAI web pages:

- User processes⁷
- Documentation for end users⁸
- Typical issues and question you can find under the section - FAQ⁹

3. Life Science AAI Operations

Technical operation of the key components of Life Science AAI components is handled by e-infrastructures, who are operating them and also improving them and enabling new functionality in the context of the technical requirements specification of Life Science AAI. Operations covers also the Life Science AAI helpdesk, documentation and processes which are designed based on the capabilities of the technical solutions provided by e-infrastructures.

To support the operational aspects the Life Science AAI web page¹⁰ was created to aggregate all information for users. It contains a description of the service including a list of benefits which it offers, design instructions for using the login button of Life Science AAI and the policies defined in the context of the service. It also covers documentation relevant to all three subjects interacting with the Life Science AAI - users, relying parties and home organisations. Based on inputs from users and communities more detailed guidelines and FAQs for users and relying parties have been added. The page also contains news and updates important to the community like Migration news or Training as well as navigation to the Service catalogue, Statistics, Health check and contact to Life Science AAI support.

⁷ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/version-2023/user.html>

⁸ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/documentation/user-documentation/user-documentation.html>

⁹ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/users/faq-for-end-users.html>

¹⁰ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/>

3.1 Current status

Life science AAI is running in production mode since the 11th of April 2022. As a part of the launch process, the ELIXIR community AAI has been migrated. This covered transferring all of the data from ELIXIR AAI into the Life Science AAI, whilst communicating this change to the users and relying parties previously connected to the ELIXIR AAI. The BBMRI-ERIC AAI has subsequently been migrated on the 9th of May 2023. This migration has been performed in the same form as the initial migration of ELIXIR infrastructure. In terms of integration of other infrastructures directly into the Life Science AAI preparatory work has been executed by the end of the project to prepare the environment and infrastructures for a full-scale integration. In most cases, the Life Science AAI can already be used as an authentication option for such infrastructures. The collection of ARIA services is also integrated utilising the Life Science AAI as an alternative authentication provider.

Life Science AAI is built on components and architecture whose capabilities were proven in deployments in other projects. This confirms that a generic solution of this type utilising the same components has been successfully demonstrated for thousands of users.

At the time of writing this deliverable, the Life Science AAI is running in a production mode, facilitating authentication and authorisation for relying parties, and can be used by active Life Science ID holders. It has enabled the login into the infrastructure using any entity present in the eduGAIN inter-federation. However, due to the excessive number of entries, they could not all be tested one by one. In addition, the Life Science AAI has enabled customers to log in via common authentication providers like Google, LinkedIn, ORCID, and Apple. As a last-resort alternative, the local username and password have been enabled for users who do not have access to any of the previously mentioned identity providers or are not willing to use them.

In addition to the components forming the basic architecture (Proxy IdP/SP and IdM systems), several other components have been deployed to support and provide additional functionality offered by the AAI:

- The implementation of a GA4GH Passport and Visa Broker to support the GA4GH Passports and Visas standard¹¹ for distributed authorisation when accessing sensitive dataset information.
- The fallback Multi-Factor Authentication component which offers to register locally managed additional authentication tokens. This component is integrated with the Life Science AAI user profile page.
- To simplify the management of the integrated Relying Parties with the Life Science AAI from the perspective of their providers, an automated tool¹² for managing the integration configuration has been deployed by the ELIXIR and BBMRI infrastructures as a pilot implementation. This application has resulted in a streamlining of the whole service management process both from the integrators and support perspectives.
- Additionally, to ease up the lookup of information about the infrastructure service uptime an integration with a traffic light monitoring output processing tool has been deployed.¹³
- To facilitate the easy discovery of the services enabled to use Life Science AAI as an authentication provider a catalogue of integrated services has been developed.¹⁴

¹¹ https://github.com/ga4gh-duri/ga4gh-duri.github.io/blob/master/researcher_ids/ga4gh_passport_v1.md

¹² <https://services.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/spreg/>, <https://services.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/bbmri-spreg/>

¹³ <https://lifesciencelogin.status.io/>

¹⁴ <https://services.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/catalogue/>

- To ease up integration from the other side of the process - the Identity providers, - a specialised tool to check the compatibility of the authentication provider with the requirements of the Life Science AAI acting as a consumer of the external identity, in this scenario has been developed and deployed.¹⁵
- A publicly accessible application displaying an overview of the access statistics and usage of the Life Science AAI has been introduced.¹⁶
- In addition to supporting demonstrations of the functionality provided by the infrastructure several relying parties have been developed and integrated into the infrastructure, e.g. GA4GH Passports and Visa tester.

For the statistics perspective (logins, service availability, number of services,..) refer to section 6 - Usage report.

3.2 New releases and acceptance environment

The Life Science AAI has two identical environments - the production and the acceptance environment. The production environment is the main one, accessible to end users and where all services are integrated. The acceptance environment is an exact copy of the production one but it is hidden from common users. Its purpose is to test new features and configuration changes before it will impact users.

The acceptance environment is especially useful for testing changes in Life Science AAI which will have an impact on user flows in the system or on the user experience in general. It gives the option to test new upgrades thoroughly and assess their impact on users. It also makes it easier to mitigate such an impact, for example, to update user documentation or notify users about upcoming changes.

Individual Life Science AAI components can usually be tested even without the acceptance environment but sometimes it is not possible to test complete functionality unless all components are in place. The acceptance environment can be also used for verifying that a new feature behaves as it was intended and there has been no misunderstanding in the requirement.

Therefore all changes in the components, regardless of whether they are new features or just maintenance updates, are deployed on the acceptance environment first. Only after acceptance by representatives is the change deployed in the production environment and made available for all users.

3.3 Test environment for new relying services

The developers of relying services want to make sure their service integration to Life Science AAI is fully tested before exposing the service to the end users. Even though the process for registering a new relying service (see the next section) is straightforward, there is some configuration and integration detail on the service side, which might be more complex. For this reason, there is a test environment for the new relying services where all services are registered first and only after the service integration is verified will it be moved to production and made available to the users.

¹⁵ <https://attributes.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://statistics.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/>

The test environment for relying services is an isolated area within the production environment of Life Science AAI. The acceptance environment described above is not used for testing new relying services because the acceptance environment is for testing and verifying new functionality for the whole Life Science AAI itself. The new relying services need to connect to a stable (production) environment where they can be tested by their developers.

The production environment and testing environment are the same in their behaviour. The only difference is that the users who can log in to the service are limited to those who have opted in for the service test environment. This setting guarantees that the service developer can test the integration themselves or with any other users if there is a need to. Moving the service from the test to the production environment is done exclusively on the Life Science AAI side, without any change on the relying service or its configuration. Therefore, if the service integration was properly tested in the test environment, there is a guarantee it will work in the production environment as well.

This environment also makes the integration process easier by dropping some requirements on the inputs that need to be provided by the services when registering for integration into the Life Science AAI. For instance, when registering into the testing environment the service does not need to have all required policies in place, as this could create an initial barrier and would not allow parallel integration and policy-making on the service side. Lesser requirements are compensated by the strict access control to the services in the test environment. As already mentioned, users of such a service are already familiar with the need to actively opt into the test environment themselves, when the application process informs them about this fact.

3.4 Process for registering a relying service

Each relying service which wants to use Life Science AAI for authentication and authorization must be registered first. During the registration process, the new relying services are first exposed to the test environment described above. The process is further described below.

Before starting the service registration process the service owner has to make sure the service's Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP), assuming already defined, is not in conflict with the Life Science AAI's AUP that all end users accept when they register their Life Science ID. The service owner can extend the Life Science AAI's AUP with service-specific extra terms but those cannot conflict with it. The service owner is also responsible for presenting the service-specific extra terms to an end user.

Step 1: Install a SAML SP or OIDC RP

The developer of the relying service is responsible for installing and configuring the necessary software to integrate into the Life Science AAI. Life Science AAI currently supports two technical protocols that a service owner can choose from

- Security Assertion Mark-up Language 2.0 (SAML 2.0), using SAML Service Provider (SP) software
- OpenID Connect (OIDC), using OIDC Relying Party (RP) software

Step 2: Register the SAML SP or OIDC RP to the Life Science AAI test environment

The Life Science AAI test environment is a sandbox where the relying service developer can test their service's integration to Life Science AAI without exposing the service to common end users.

1. The service developer has to have a Life Science ID or register it for themselves.
2. The service developer has to decide what user attributes (user information) will be needed for the SP/RP.
3. The service developer has to register the SP or RP in Life Science AAI using the SP Registry page: https://webapp.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/sp_request
4. The Life Science AAI operator checks the data and informs the service developer that the service is registered to the Life Science AAI test environment.
5. For a consistent user experience, the Life Science AAI has published design guidelines for the login page of the SP/RP that the service developer is encouraged to adopt.
6. The service developer needs to decide if Life Science AAI should enforce access to the service based on the user's membership in a particular group, the user having a sufficient level of assurance, or any other attribute.
7. The service developer should configure their
 - SAML SP to consume the Life Science AAI proxy IdP's SAML2 metadata file: <https://mdx.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/entities/https%3A%2F%2Fproxy.aai.lifescience-ri.eu%2Fmetadata%2Fbackend.xml>
 - OIDC RP to point the OIDC well-known configuration endpoint: <https://proxy.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/.well-known/openid-configuration>

Step 3: Move the SP/RP from Life Science AAI test to Life Science AAI production environment

When the service developer has tested their service sufficiently in the test environment, they need to contact the Life Science AAI support desk and ask to move the service to the production environment.

While the procedure has been well established for the Life Science AAI, the migrated communities - ELIXIR, and BBMRI have started to develop and pilot an alternative mechanism working in a more automated fashion for steps 2 point 3. This approach is based on deploying a different standalone application letting managers log in and manage the integration settings via the concept of creating a request for changes. The rest of the procedure stays the same - an operator reviews the request and by approving it the proposed changes are automatically propagated into the relevant interfaces.

3.5 Process for onboarding new identity providers

All external identity providers (IdP) compatible with SAML2, OIDC or OAuth2 protocols can be technically integrated into the Life Science AAI. Currently, there are two kinds of IdPs integrated: Academic identity providers which are available via the research and education identity federation eduGAIN, and commercial or community identity providers like Google and ORCID.

Commercial and community IdPs can be easily onboarded because the project has decided to support only a few of them, making it possible to test them completely. With eduGAIN, the situation is more complicated. The project integrates all IdPs from eduGAIN to offer the option to use home organisation IdP for as many users as possible. However, there are thousands of IdPs in eduGAIN and, therefore, it is not possible to verify the integration will work for all of them. The verification is complicated by the fact that normally a valid account in the IdP is needed to do it, but the accounts

are usually available only for users from the institution which operates the IdP. Therefore, there is no technical option to fully automate such a verification process and scale it for all eduGAIN IdPs.

The Life Science AAI has adopted an onboarding process where all eduGAIN IdPs are initially integrated on a technical level but not exposed to be available for the users. During the sign-in process, the users are presented with a list of only those IdPs which have been demonstrated to work. Users are provided with an option to try to sign in using another IdP which has not been demonstrated to work, with a warning that the sign-in might fail. If the user manages to successfully sign in with such an IdP, the onboarding process will be completed in the background which results in the IdP being fully enabled. In the future, an additional process will be added which will cancel the onboarding of an IdP where problems have been detected.

To integrate a custom-requested Identity Provider, a standardised procedure has been developed. This flow can be initiated either from the user of an Identity Provider or its operator or from the Life Science AAI operators. The procedure can be briefly summarised in the following steps:

1. A contact between the Life Science AAI team and the Identity provider operator is established:
 - a. A user/operator of the Identity Provider contacts the Life Science AAI support team via email and requests the Identity provider to be added.
 - b. The Life Science AAI operators proactively contact the operator of Identity provider. The initial message includes a formal *Letter to encourage home organisation IdPs to release attributes*¹⁷ signed by the Life Science AAI representatives.
2. Set up the Life Science AAI as a service-consuming authentication on the side of the Identity provider. This part is done by the requesting entity.
3. Set up the requested Identity Provider on the side of Life Science AAI as one of the login alternatives. This part is done by the Life Science AAI operators.
4. Demonstrate the integration works by logging into an attribute conformance check service operated by the Life Science AAI using the integrated Identity Provider.

In the described procedure, steps 2 and 3 are usually run in parallel to speed up the integration. In the future, the process could be streamlined by deploying a management tool similar to the Relying party management which would ease the technical integration part on the side of Life Science AAI operators by automatically provisioning the registered metadata of the Identity Provider.

3.6 Helpdesk

Helpdesk processes are crucial for the smooth operations of Life Science AAI because users need to authenticate to services and any interruption is preventing them from doing their work. Moreover, due to the distributed nature of the environment and usage of identity federations, some of the workflows might be complex and inexperienced users might have problems navigating through them. Even though there is ongoing work to enhance the user experience, there will always be users who will need help to solve their issues.

Apart from end users, the helpdesk has to support also the technical part of the AAI, like connecting new services, changes in the service integration, questions about technical aspects of the AAI and so on. The last aspect of the helpdesk is to handle any questions and requests related to the AAI, which might be both technical and non-technical.

¹⁷ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/lis-login/home-organization/home-organizations.html>

Based on the requirements above it is clear that the helpdesk must be able to represent the LS community as well as the e-infrastructures responsible for the technical implementation of Life Science AAI. It was agreed the helpdesk be structured in three layers. Layer 1 support (L1) handles the initial contact with the requester, gathers relevant information and offers basic bits of advice (eg. provides documentation). L2 handles advanced problems which don't require technical expertise. L3 is for technical issues which require technical debugging or fixing problems on the service side.

For the L1 helpdesk it is crucial to know the users and their requirements. Therefore, L1 is handled by the life sciences community. L3 is strictly technical, so it is handled by the operators of the individual components. Currently, e-infrastructures are the only ones that are operating such components, but in the future, there is an expectation of specialised services operated by the life science community, which will mean L3 support even for those.

Level 2 helpdesk can be handled by either the life science community or the e-infrastructures. The initial proposal from e-infrastructures contained L2 operated by them, but during the implementation and pilot run of Life Science AAI, it was discovered that both L1 and L2 can be handled by a single team, which might even speed up the resolution of requests. After discussions and testing of the two approaches, L2 was decided to be operated by the same team as L1.

3.7 Documentation

Documentation is tightly related to helpdesk processes. Both L1 and L2 helpdesks need technical documentation to be able to navigate users and help with their problems. The technical documentation is provided by the e-infrastructures that are developing, configuring and operating individual components of Life Science AAI. Based on that the documentation for end users and user-facing services operators has been published on the project and infrastructure website. This task has been identified as the future competency of the L1 helpdesk because it has to take into account the specifics of the Life Science AAI users and the terminology, they are accustomed to using. For the duration of the project, the documentation has been provided mainly by the infrastructure operations teams as they have been in close touch with the development and deployment teams.

The process was established within the Technical working group, which describes how the technical documentation is created by e-infrastructures, discussed within the Technical WG and passed to the operations teams, who are creating and publishing user-facing documentation and manuals on the Life Science AAI web page¹⁸.

3.8 Service Improvements

For the further service improvement of the Life Science AAI after the project ends the methodology for service quality measurements for end users and services should be prepared. One of the main tools will be a regular survey aimed at Relying Parties and then analysing the results and planning the improvements. Before the project end, there is a plan for a first round basic survey. More information about the survey can be found in the chapter User Experience continuous improvements.

¹⁸ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/>

4. ARIA access management for EOSC-Life RIs

ARIA access management is used across several research infrastructures on the ESFRI road map and TNA projects. It is primarily developed by Instruct-ERIC. In CORBEL, ARIA was used as a platform for exploring opportunities to identify cross-RI use cases and automating parts of access management. To further the goals of cross-RI applications it was clear that ARIA needed additional enhancements to the existing functionality. ARIA has been also extended with the functionality to better manage independent calls. This improvement was utilised in the open calls of EOSC-Life.

4.1 ARIA Development enhancements to meet RI use cases

Extending ARIA to meet existing use cases across the RIs that utilise it for management functions is essential for both the operations of RIs and for identifying opportunities to share experience on management and implementation of calls, access and delivery of access (whether to data or physical infrastructure). In this tranche of work, the focus has been put on extending calls management to integrate a powerful automated peer review system from the access management side of the application. Also, it looked at visits management and an extensive user experience review has been performed with the outcomes being implemented. A significant uplift in terms of new functionality to allow facilities to better report on visit progress has been recorded. To be compatible with Life Science AAI, as well as to take advantage of modern authentication technologies and best practices, a new authentication system for ARIA was launched.

4.1.1 Integrated review of calls management

Automated review is a significant feature of ARIA and has been essential to the platform since its inception. There are two mechanisms by which users can submit an application/proposal to ARIA, one of them is through the access management system, which has a whole management package around visits, and delivery of access. The second mechanism is calls, which is a much more streamlined mechanism of application management with much simpler post-award management and reporting. It became clear that, whilst the two mechanisms are valuable to be distinct methods of managing applications, the automated peer review would be very valuable to call management in addition to access.

Peer review of applications in calls has been implemented identically to the feature set in access management. At either call creation or by editing the call at a later point the call administrator can define two pools of users named “moderators” and “reviewers”.

An application can only have one moderator assigned to it. The role of the moderator is to decide on the proposal, choosing to approve or reject it. They can do this at any point after they are assigned to the proposal by a call administrator. This role is used in many different ways by different call administrators, sometimes this is a representative of a review panel, sometimes they are part of the review team for the access, or alternatively, this role is assumed by a call administrator. Once they are assigned to the proposal they are invited, via email, to assign a number of reviewers to the application. Once the minimum number of reviewers have completed their review the moderator is informed that the application is eligible to be actioned. When they action the proposal they can either choose to approve or reject it. Each call can have completely independently configured forms for both review and moderation.

Reviewers, when they are assigned to review an application, are informed via email with a simple one-click link which will (after login) take them directly to a page with all the information they need to review. On this page, they are given the review scoring form, the application detail and any guidelines they may need to complete the review. Should the application be actioned before their review is completed they will be informed that their review is no longer required. If they are not able to review for any reason then there is a link for them to indicate this in the initial email they receive. If this causes the total number of available reviewers below the minimum threshold for the call then the moderator will be informed to add another reviewer to the team.

4.1.2 Visit management improvements

As part of tracking the delivery of access, “visits management” is the system in ARIA where facilities can detail the relevant information. The term ‘visit’ is somewhat of a misnomer as this system is capable of tracking access whether it be physical, remote or indeed digital access to the service/technology. Utilising this visit management, the facility can keep the user clearly up to date with the exact progress of their project and report metrics regarding the access to the infrastructure. A long-standing feature of visit management is integrated scheduling for physical access and configurable ‘steps’ for remote access. It was clear through discussions with facilities and access providers that these were not all-encompassing. As such, a project to enhance the visits management to better track the delivery of access and give facilities more tools for enhancing management of projects have been started.

To begin with, an extensive user experience review of ARIA’s toolset to understand the missing requirements in the software has been performed. From this, it was clear that several gaps lie in the separation of the handling of ‘physical’ and ‘remote’ access. While ARIA created a distinction in how these visits were managed, the reality is that facilities may require a mixture of both. Physical access may require several ‘steps’ to be completed before the scheduling of an instrument can take place. Additionally, remote access may still need to be scheduled on an instrument as part of delivering the access. A proposal was initiated for a new unified access workflow that would allow for remote and physical access, to have separately configured workflows with ‘checkpoints’ (an evolution of the previous ‘steps’ mechanism for the remote access) with the capacity for custom checkpoints having integrated functionality (such as instrument scheduling/booking).

With the help of EU-OpenScreen, some gaps in the visit tracking features were identified and plans for adding two new features for these checkpointed workflows. This has resulted in the development of the ‘notebook’ feature where the facility and the access users can add information, files and other data to the checkpoints on access. This has become a key feature as more use is made of remote since the COVID-19 pandemic. Another feature was developed in collaboration with the University of Leeds, one of the access providers within the Instruct-ERIC RI and EU-OpenScreen, in order to capture some financial information around the delivery of access.

Mock-up of ARIA visit management, showing visit workflow sessions and 'notebook' feature

Having identified all of the core user stories and use cases of the visits management section, an upgraded wireframe prototype respecting the new procedures has been built. Armed with these prototypes contact with key stakeholders was established and it has been identified within the user storying process to do some user tests and iterate on the wireframes based on feedback. This activity resulted in designing the visit-view that is shown above.

Once all the prototypes were in place the work on upgrading the backend functionality to incorporate the new features and implementation of the new UI started. This new UI and features were presented at the ARIA workshop in February 2020 held jointly with CORBEL, iNEXT-Discovery and Instruct-ULTRA comprising 40 participants. The changes were released for general consumption in April 2020.

4.1.3 Upgrading ARIA authentication and authorisation to adopt Life Science AAI

As ARIA grows it became clear that it cannot continue to use SAML2 as a primary authentication technology. SAML2 is largely a stateful authentication mechanism which relies heavily on browser sessions to maintain the state between different page loads. It also relies on the web server responding to the request to maintain a session of the user's information to perform a successful authentication. ARIA now has multiple services that make up the whole application, so delegating tasks to those services with SAML2 in an authenticated way is challenging and requires complex state management. As such an OpenID Connect authentication mechanism has been implemented for all of the services inside the ARIA application.

The existing user database of ARIA is large with over 15,000 users. Migrating to Life Science AAI is a complex issue, further compounded by the nature of the users that make up this database. For the most part, ARIA users are wet-lab scientists who are not experts in data tools or computation. As a result, authentication must be completely seamless and easy for these users and should not introduce additional hurdles. Migrating the user database cannot be done automatically for several reasons, both technical and procedural. As such ARIA needs to be in a position to take advantage of a multi-stage migration process that allows the user community to grow in confidence in the Life Science AAI service.

The stages proposed were Implementation, Migration and Adoption. In the first phase, users can opt-in to log in via Life Science AAI through an option on the ARIA login interface. Secondly, in the Migration phase, the Life Science AAI login will be prominently featured as the main mechanism to log in, with other options still available, but less prominent. These first two phases have been completed, the final Adoption phase will be to present Life Science AAI as the only login option, with all existing mechanisms to login disabled, for selected life science communities that use ARIA.

To ensure that all three phases can be supported properly, the identity and access management service has been separated from the ARIA-core software. A Keycloak authentication service has been set up to provide the IAM platform for ARIA and we built a custom adapter to allow users to migrate to this new authentication technology without any form of interruption or change to their logins. Passwords are fully migrated on their first login to the platform and no action is required from the user outside of accepting additional terms and conditions for the identity platform.

4.2 Implementation of ARIA to support EOSC-Life Calls

ARIA has been used in EOSC-Life for open calls in the three work packages WP9 (training), WP1 (data sets), and WP3 (open calls). The implementations for each of these calls were slightly different and tailored to the needs of that specific call.

The WP9 training call utilised the ARIA calls management software as tracking of delivery of access was not relevant for the call. A custom theme has been implemented for ARIA based on the EOSC-Life website and branding toolkit. This is essential for any setup of ARIA as the user must not feel lost when they arrive at the application system. The WP also worked with the team in WP9 to ensure all the correct questions and configurable options were implemented correctly. The automated review system discussed in 3.1.1 of this report was not ready at the time of this call, so review and reports were handled manually.

The WP1 internal call again utilised the same ARIA calls management software. However, new developments were implemented that allow the automation of the peer review for these applications. No additional templating was required as the style from the WP9 template was already generic enough to fit this use case nicely.

The WP3 open call was slightly more complex in terms of the review procedure so it was decided to use the access management system for this call. Slight modifications to the existing template were implemented to add the “contact the experts” buttons to the process and to include an EOSC-Life call dashboard where applicants could see all currently open EOSC-Life Open Calls, along with past and present applications, all in one place. More information on the processes implemented for this call can be found in D3.1 of the EOSC-Life project [EOSC20].

4.3 Implementation of ARIA to support EOSC-Life Research Infrastructures

As part of widening access to the ARIA access management software WP5 has been working with individual research infrastructures within EOSC-Life to set up their processes in ARIA. At the time of the deliverable the following items have been implemented:

Infrastructure	Project	Implementation
MIRRI	IS_MIRRI 21	DPA signed Contract agreed Integrated template Access route(s) configured Open for access
EMBRC	EMBRC (RI)	DPA signed Contract signed Integrated template Access route(s) configured Open for access
EU-OpenScreen	EU-OpenScreen DRIVE	DPA signed Contract agreed Integrated template Access route(s) configured Open for access

5. BBMRI Negotiator and related tools

The BBMRI-ERIC (Biobanking and BioMolecular Resources Research Infrastructure - European Research Infrastructure Consortium) Negotiator is a Service that provides an efficient communication platform for biobankers and operators requesting samples and/or data. It substantially simplifies the communication steps necessary to obtain information on the availability of relevant samples/data, particularly if the researchers need to communicate with multiple candidate biobanks.

The purpose of the negotiator is to serve academic researchers seeking bio-specimen and data for their research by providing a place for structured negotiations with partner biobanks. By streamlining the entire negotiation process the BBMRI-ERIC negotiator facilitates access and simplifies communication about the availability of samples and data for research between researchers and BBMRI-ERIC biobanks.

In a recent development, this tool has been extended to support a more general negotiation process not tied only to a biobank. In particular, in the canSERV project, the Negotiator is used to handle the process of providing controlled access to services supporting researchers in their work, e.g. disease models, data samples, open digital research services, or training.

5.1 Negotiator workflow

Users of the Negotiator can be put into two categories: resource owners and researchers. The resource owner role represents a person owning some data to which the access should be negotiated. Primarily, such people are representatives of a particular resource (biobank, service) who are managing access to the resource, but also can have any other roles in the infrastructure such as biobank network managers, national node managers and so on. The researcher role represents an individual that wants to access the resource and use it in their research.

5.1.1 Researcher workflow

The workflow starts with the researcher identifying the candidate biobanks that own potentially interesting data samples. The researcher can identify and select biobanks/collections of interest in any one of the BBMRI-ERIC discovery services such as the Directory, Locator or Finder (more detailed description can be found in the next section). After finding the candidate biobanks, the researchers file a request to start the resource access negotiation process. To submit a request the researcher needs to describe the project for which the resource will be used and describe the request, and they can also add an ethics code and attachments such as Material Transfer Agreement (MTA) or Data Transfer Agreement (DTA). On submitting the request, the negotiation process starts. The request is first verified by the BBMRI-ERIC, both in an automated and manual way, to check if the request is sensible. If so, the request is forwarded to the resource representatives for further review. The researcher negotiates with the candidate biobanks and refines the request, if needed. Each biobank then flags the availability of the data. The researcher can then select the biobanks and data samples they want to use and signs the relevant MTA or DTA with each biobank. The system then provides access to tracking for the delivery of the data. When the research project is finished, the researcher flags this and offers data, as appropriate, for return.

5.1.2 Resource owner workflow

The workflow from the resource owner perspective starts by registering the resource in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory. When the resource is made available for access negotiation, its representatives register for this role. When a request is filed that concerns the resource a person is representing, they get an email notification. By accessing the Negotiator they can manage the negotiation process by requesting that the applicant refines the request and indicating the resource availability. The representative can also track resource delivery and the data return process.

5.2 Interaction with related tools

The Negotiator as a service requires additional supporting tools to enable its functionality. Such support is provided by the BBMRI Directory, BBMRI Sample Locator and BBMRI Finder.

5.2.1 BBMRI Directory

The BBMRI Directory service is an online platform developed to serve as a comprehensive directory or catalogue of biobanks and related resources across Europe. It provides a centralised platform for researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders to search and discover information about biobanks, their data/sample collections, and associated data.

The Directory service offers a user-friendly interface that allows users to explore and navigate through the database of registered biobanks. It provides detailed information about each biobank, including its location, contact information, the scope of collections, available sample types, data availability, and any specific research focus or expertise of the biobank.

Researchers can use the BBMRI Directory to identify and locate specific biobanks that might hold relevant biological samples and associated data for their research projects. The service allows users to search for biobanks based on various criteria, such as geographic location, disease focus, sample types, and specific research domains. Additionally, it may provide additional resources and

information beyond biobank listings. It may include information about other research infrastructures, data resources, and services that are relevant to biobanking and biomedical research.

The BBMRI Directory service aims to foster collaboration and promote the sharing of resources within the biobanking community by providing a centralised platform for discovering and connecting with biobanks and related resources. It helps researchers to identify and access the samples and data they need for their research projects more efficiently.

5.2.2 BBMRI Sample Locator

The BBMRI Sample Locator service is a platform developed by the BBMRI-ERIC. It serves as a centralised platform for searching and locating biological samples stored in various biobanks across Europe. These samples are valuable resources for conducting research and advancing our understanding of diseases, diagnostics, and treatment options.

The Sample Locator service provides researchers with a convenient way to discover and request access to specific types of samples for their research projects. It allows users to search for samples based on different criteria such as disease type, sample type, age range, and geographic location. The service provides a user-friendly interface that enables researchers to browse and filter through the available sample collections efficiently.

When researchers find samples of interest, the Sample Locator service facilitates the connection between the researcher and the Negotiator to start the access negotiation process with the biobank that holds the samples. The Sample Locator service aims to promote collaboration and maximise the use of existing biobank resources. It reduces duplication of effort and enhances the efficiency of research projects that rely on biological samples by providing a centralised platform for sample discovery.

5.3 Interactions with the Life Science AAI

Due to the need to know the identity of the people involved in the negotiation process the Negotiator uses the Life Science AAI as an authentication gateway. The authentication flow follows the standard set of steps resulting in a familiar login procedure for anyone accessing services integrated with the Life Science AAI. After successful authentication, the Negotiator consumes basic information about the user (name, email) and the LS ID serves as the primary identifier of the user in the system. By leveraging authentication to the AAI and also connecting the supporting services to the AAI this creates an environment where users can hop between the services without the need to re-authenticate.

The Life Science AAI also facilitates the functionality of registering as a resource representative in the Negotiator service. To register into such a role a user needs to access a specially crafted registration form, which first asks for authentication using the LS ID. Then the user needs to specify the IDs of the resources which they want to represent and submit the form. The application is reviewed and processed by the designated persons from BBMRI. If the application is approved, the user is assigned as a member of a group in the Life Science AAI Perun system (identity management part) that represents the role of representatives for the resource with the specified ID.

A group expressing the representative role of the resource is managed in an automated fashion. A synchronisation mechanism periodically scans the list of available resources by querying the aggregated API exposed by the Negotiator, which ultimately collects all resources from the different

Directories connected to the Negotiator. When the synchronisation detects a new resource has been added and it does not have a corresponding group representing the administrative role in the Identity Management part of AAI, such a group is created by the mechanism and configured for the provisioning, which is the next part of the interaction of Negotiator and AAI. Similar clean-up synchronisation is set up for removing obsolete representations of the roles for resources that are no longer present in the infrastructure.

The provisioning mechanism is responsible for delivering the information about persons with the representative role to the Negotiator. When a person is granted this role, the provisioning engine of the Life Science AAI detects this fact and starts the delivery of the updated data to the Negotiator. This process is based on generating two JSON¹⁹ files and uploading them to the Negotiator API. The first file contains information about the users - name, identifier, affiliations, organisation and data for being able to link with the data present in the other file. The second file carries information about the group objects representing the resource with which the role of being representative is associated. Namely, it contains the information about the resource - identifier, source directory and list of linkage data to establish a connection with the user file - which users have the representative role. The negotiator processes these files after the upload is finished and modifies the permissions in the web application, resulting in allowing access to the relevant agendas.

6. Usage report

Life Science AAI was launched in production mode on the 11th of April 2022. Together with the act of starting up the infrastructure, the first of the participating RIs - ELIXIR AAI - has been migrated. As a result, the Life Science AAI has been from the start usable by approximately 9000 LS ID holders being able to access approximately 150 relying services in the production environment.

Immediately after the service was launched, it recorded a huge increase in the number of AAI accounts. By the end of June 2022, the number of active LS ID holders had increased to almost 10,500, with 1500 registering for the LS ID. The previously observed situation spanning one year in ELIXIR AAI has been observed to average around a thousand new accounts per year. In terms of integrating relying services, the number in a production environment is almost identical to at the launch date, while approximately 10 services are now obsolete and have been disconnected. A similar number of services have been promoted or integrated into the production environment. An interesting development has been identified in the utilisation of the local username and password as an alternative to logging in via home organisation. This option has been a game changer if the Identity Providers are not correctly configured with the Life Science AAI (despite being prompted in advance to adjust their settings even before the migration). By the end of June 2022, almost 100 AAI accounts have activated this alternative login mechanism. From the perspective of new features, the Life Science AAI has introduced a public list of integrated relying services providing information to the users about what services users can access using their LS ID. Another new simplifying feature for users has been the introduction of self-activation for the local username and password using the AAI profile page, replacing the procedure routed via the L1 and L2 support teams.

By September 2022, the number of active LS IDs used increased to over 11,300. The number of relying services integrated to use Life Science AAI as an option for logging into the service has been observed to drop slightly but oscillate around the number 150 in the production environment.

¹⁹ JSON - JavaScript Object Notation (<https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc8259>)

Despite not seeing an increase in this number, over 15 new services have been registered in the test environment. The local username and password alternative for logging in has been activated by almost 50 more users. The Life Science AAI introduced a publicly available health-check page,²⁰ where users and relying services operators can check if the AAI is experiencing downtime. This feature has been accompanied by making access statistics²¹ publicly available, giving an overview of how many logins were made per day, and detailed statistics for relying parties and identity providers focusing on the same information.

By the end of 2022, Life Science AAI has provided over 12,200 LS IDs, whose holders were able to access more than 146 production services, while more than 150 have been registered in the testing environment, waiting to be tested, or promoted into the production environment. The local username and password have become the 7th most popular login alternative, activated by over 240 users, with the social identity providers being the top three options. During this time, the team has started preparations for the migration of BBMRI AAI into the Life Science AAI. Because of this preparatory work, the primary focus on delivering major features has been to fill missing functionalities of BBMRI AAI.

Advancing to March 2023, more than 700 new LS IDs were registered, making approximately 12,900 LS IDs registered in the system. In terms of integration with relying services, the AAI has been enabled by 145 productions relying services, with an increase of services being registered into the testing environment to 165 cases.

In terms of handling the requests, Life Science AAI has been from the start serving approximately 6000 logins per month. With the increasing number of registered LS ID holders, by March 2023 the number has been constantly increasing reaching nearly 14,000 logins per month, with peaks of 700 logins per day.

As a result of the BBMRI AAI migration happening in May 2023, the user base has been extended by more than 1200 new LS ID holders. The migration also brought new relying parties integrated into the Life Science AAI ecosystem. In particular, it has increased the number of production services by 12 and testing services by 15.

At the time of writing this deliverable, Life Science AAI provides access to 165 integrated relying services in the production environment, while 189 other relying services are integrated into the testing environment. These services can be accessed by 14,213 LS ID holders. Users have used 228 identity providers, either to register for an account or link it as an alternative login mechanism. The local username and password have been activated by 571 users. In terms of login requests, the AAI has handled 13123 logins during the last month.

The overview of the adoption is summarised in the table and graph below.

Date	LS IDs registered	Registered RPs (prod / test env.)	Local username and passwords activated	Logins per month
04/2022 (Launch)	~ 9000	~ 150 / 160	0	~ 6000
06/2022	~ 10 500	~ 150 / 165	~ 100	~ 7500

²⁰ <https://lifesciencelogin.status.io/>

²¹ <https://statistics.aai.lifescience-ri.eu/>

09/2022	~ 11 300	~ 150 / 160	~ 150	~ 7650
12/2022	~ 12 200	~ 146 / 150	~ 240	~ 7650
03/2023	~ 12 900	~ 145 / 160	~ 280	~ 11 800
05/2023	~ 14 100	~ 160 / 175	~ 300	~ 14 000
06/2023	14 351	165 / 189	571	13123

Report documents:

The following documents summarise the operation, development and community migration status for 1-3 periods from the production date to the date of this document delivery as reported to WP5.

- 14. 4. 2022 - Report for WP5 after migration²²
- 26. 5. 2022 - Report for WP5 Migration 26.5.2022²³
- 29. 6. 2022 - Report for WP5 Migration 29.6.2022²⁴
- 15. 9. 2022 - Report for WP5 Task 5.3 15.9.2022²⁵
- 8. 12. 2022 - Report for WP5 Task 5.3 8.12.2022²⁶
- 2. 3. 2023 - Report for WP5 Task 5.3 2.3.2023²⁷
- 16.6.2023 - Report for WP5 Task 5.3 16.6.2023²⁸

²² https://docs.google.com/document/d/1w_XGNxbySxXhnfiYevx4GnLRa35wESrU9TSktfGnHZA/edit

²³ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1sLmKbRt0BLtCQzQ9HprXE1m_FX_r3cZ1DpzngjSE28/edit?usp=share_link

²⁴ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1QsJs5fvFU8BktwYIMTWIye2vKRQ-xeP6KxZHed1dqSU/edit?usp=share_link

²⁵ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1hfkxp0lAX0RMvuql_tB7cqvcyiP9Xl9XpJYyl-hx5Ag/edit

²⁶ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1z6ur_gRRe1hNJR5NbPoNeGUhYQoLanNtbTyLNuYVVGw/edit-heading=h.k7ado2lttrr8

²⁷ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1oRAJdiOXuXFAe7axg64qr7PGHEvhI9-wzeW9YjI4xGA/edit-heading=h.k7ado2lttrr8>

²⁸ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uZmfKvh8tIUefoyDlPkl1eODa2ORI9T0pWdkzUlzQg/edit>

7. Outcomes

The specific outcomes of the EOSC-Life project related to the Life Science AAI include:

- **Infrastructure Development:** The project established the technical infrastructure necessary for implementing the Life Science AAI. This involved designing and deploying authentication and authorization mechanisms, protocols, and services to enable secure access to life science data and resources.
- **Federated Identity Management:** The project established a federated identity management system, allowing researchers to use their institutional credentials to access resources and services within the EOSC-Life ecosystem. This streamlined access and simplified the authentication process for researchers, primarily by consolidating the infrastructures run by the participating RIs into a single infrastructure, usable by all of them, with the intention of unifying the environment and consolidating the operation of the infrastructure.
- **Interoperability and Integration:** The project aimed to ensure interoperability and integration of the Life Science AAI with existing infrastructures, data repositories, and research platforms. This allows researchers to seamlessly access and utilise data and tools from multiple sources, promoting collaboration and data sharing.
- **Security and Privacy:** The work carried out aimed to address security and privacy concerns associated with the Life Science AAI. This involves implementing robust security measures and data protection protocols and ensuring compliance with relevant regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- **Training and Support:** The project aimed to provide training and support to researchers, administrators, and developers to facilitate the adoption and effective use of the Life Science AAI. This included organising workshops, documentation, and community engagement activities to promote awareness and understanding of the infrastructure.

8. Next Steps

The Life Science AAI has gained the status of a heavily used Authentication and Authorization service since its launch. The full-scale migration of the big RIs (ELIXIR, BBMRI), and partial migrations (ARIA) are clear demonstrations of the LS clusters' interest in such a service and the need of having such a tool in place. It is also the most mature example of a cluster wide implementation of the AARC Blueprint for AAI in European Research Infrastructures and EOSC.

Despite gaining such a status the platform will require further financial and technical support, especially in terms of further technical evolution with new challenges and customers requirements as they arise. The following chapters are devoted to the already planned extensions and follow-up projects where Life Science AAI plays its role and the challenges for Life Science AAI as a product.

8.1 Planned extensions

This section summarises the already planned technical and conceptual extensions of the Life Science AAI. In the case of these evolutionary steps, the work has already begun but has not been finished by the time of writing this deliverable.

8.1.1 Connecting with Industry

Approaching the end of the project several use cases were identified in which where the eduGAIN inter-federation Identity Providers have been identified as insufficient. The reasoning is primarily that commercial subjects are not part of this Identity Provider group and there is a growing overlap of the commercial (industry) Life Science industry organisations and users with those in academic Research and Education. Typically, potential users coming from industry often don't have access to an Identity provider from academic research or education. This issue is not mitigated by the possibility of using commercial and social identity providers (Google, LinkedIn, ORCID, ...), given understandable barriers in the infrastructures to using such identity providers for accessing potentially sensitive data and the lack of identity vetting for these IdPs.

The solution is simple - the list of Identity providers could be extended by integrating the Identity Providers of the commercial industry partners and providing them as alternative login providers. However, such an activity needs to be strictly coordinated and well documented to satisfy the necessary identity verification requirements and considering the manageability of incorporating this much wider set of integrated identity providers.

8.1.2 Improved Identity Vetting support via eID integration

The need to increase verification of the original user identity is a logical evolution of the infrastructure. The requirement has been identified particularly in the context of working with more and more sensitive data (e.g. GDI project described below), where capturing a strongly verified identity is essential. Due to these facts, the project team has started investigating the possibility of integration with the eID frameworks (eIDAS in the EU) as another alternative login possibility. Early in the process, the fact that the identity itself should be used only for verification and auditing purposes has been identified since relying parties will not be able to process the eID identities due to lack of access to the national public registries.

8.1.3 Evolution of the GA4GH standards support

The GA4GH Passport and Visa standards have been evolving during the project. As this framework has been identified as one of the critical authorization mechanisms for the relying parties in genomics and health, the Life Science AAI has been implementing up-to-date versions of the standards. The Life Science AAI will closely follow this activity in the post-project operation of the infrastructure.

8.1.4 User Experience and continuous improvement

A supplementary planned activity alongside the technical evolution of the platform is to also cooperate with the users on improving the look and feel of the platform and in supporting their workflows by continuous evaluation of the user experience. Continuous development of the user interfaces and processes are expected after the project ends. Namely, the simplification of the registration workflow, login process and extension of the relevant functionality is expected. Also, the simplification of the login process is expected, as discussed previously.

As mentioned in the previous chapters on Usability and Operation, Life Science AAI service quality measurements for end users and services will be designed and implemented. The plan is to run a survey in the predesigned tool and analyse results on a regular basis. An option of continuous

feedback gathering for some of the processes should be considered (e.g. optional feedback after registration).

Before the project ends there is still a plan for the first round of the basic questionnaire (survey), but the results are not known at the time of delivering this report. The first round questionnaire will be split into two parts - for end users and the Relying Parties providers.

As for the users, no similar survey has been run in the past (no survey of quality of service before or after migration), so the focus will be on the general satisfaction and feedback of the users. For the future, we are considering gathering more elaborate and relevant data from the Relying Party providers directly, e.g. by preparing a questionnaire for the quality of their service (or set of services) targeted at particular groups of users.

In the first survey, the following topics will be covered:

- the quality of the provided support,
- overview and knowledge about the channels for getting support,
- communication (both support and operators team) and documentation,
- general satisfaction and feedback on using the service.

The Relying Party aimed questionnaire will focus on the following topics:

- support/channels for support and communication with Life Science AAI operators (also eg. missing channels or support),
- documentation and guidelines (e.g. Is the documentation satisfactory? Do users have many questions because they do not understand how to login/register? What are typical errors/problems users are facing?...)
- What kind of problems are Relying Parties facing or what functionalities/features they are missing?

Survey results will help continue improving the user experience and the quality of the service.

8.1.5 Improvements in the processes for managing integrated Relying Parties and Identity Providers

At the time of writing this deliverable, WP5 has established well-defined processes for integrating both Relying Parties and Identity Providers. Following such procedures has soon shown the need to streamline such processes in a more automated way. The WP has identified a potential for such activity to be handled by a specialised component that would simplify the process in an automated fashion, meaning the integrators would get a clear overview of the current integration setup and could easily adjust it in case of changes. Due to the vision of specialised tools for handling such activities, the processes will need to be adjusted aiming to simplify such processes as much as possible.

8.1.6 Registration into the Life Science AAI and communities as a user

The basic idea of being able to use the Life Science AAI from the user's point of view is the registration into the environment to create a user account. This registration can quickly become quite a complex process, especially if the user registers during a service login flow, and in cases when the service requires additional registration into a community (e.g. BBMRI VO) and only allows access for members of an organisational unit (e.g. research group managed by the community node). The WP has already identified the requirement to simplify such a procedure as much as possible, in order

to consolidate the flow of steps into as few as possible, with the ability to return to the flow at any time, provide means to redirect users back into the login flow etc. Many of these minor functionalities are already in place but have not been adopted to date. Next steps can be summarised in two sub-tasks: The first subtask would be to improve the capabilities of the registration system - e.g. define the flow on the side of the AAI and enforce its usage; The second subtask will be responsible for educating Relying Parties and providing support in the configuration of such flows.

8.1.7 Centralised consent management

All data flows from the AAI to a Relying Party have been implemented as requiring the user to consent if they wish to allow the data to be transferred. Such a concept highlights the need to have the ability to manage such grants, especially revoking them and getting an overview of the granted consents. At the time of writing the deliverable, no such option is provided. Instead, a procedure for getting the overview and revoking the consent has been established. In the future, this needs to be replaced by a tool provided to the users. Work has already started for implementing such overview and management places in the components that are handling the consent. However, this has been done in a non-centralised fashion since these components are not represented as a single component and are backed up by different software. The future work will consolidate all these component interfaces into a single place from which the consent can be managed.

8.2 Relevant follow-up projects

At the time of writing this deliverable, the Life Science AAI has already been identified as an essential component in many other projects, ongoing and proposed. It has been proposed as an essential service for EOSC projects to design and build Trusted Research Environments (TREs), and a proposal to further extend the AARC project where the infrastructure will serve as an early demonstrator and implementer of the proposed standards, solutions, and features. A short list of the ongoing projects in which Life Science AAI is involved, follows.

8.2.1 GDI

The European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project is enabling access to genomic and related phenotypic and clinical data across Europe. It is doing this by establishing a federated, sustainable and secure infrastructure to access the data. It builds on the outputs of the Beyond 1 Million Genomes (B1MG)²⁹ project and is realising the ambition of the 1+Million Genomes (1+MG) initiative.³⁰

This project is an initiative aimed at establishing a coordinated and harmonised framework for the management and sharing of genomic data across Europe. It seeks to address the challenges associated with the rapidly growing volume of genomic data generated by research institutions, hospitals, and sequencing centres.

EGDI's primary objective is to create a data infrastructure that enables the secure and efficient sharing of genomic data while ensuring privacy and data protection. It aims to facilitate data access,

²⁹ <https://b1mg-project.eu/>

³⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>

interoperability, and collaboration among researchers and institutions involved in genomics research and clinical applications.

The project focuses on developing common standards, protocols, and tools for data management, data integration, and data analysis in the field of genomics. It aims to harmonise data formats and establish data-sharing policies that promote open and responsible data sharing. EGDI also emphasises the importance of data security and privacy. It works on developing mechanisms and frameworks to protect sensitive genomic data while enabling controlled and authorised access for research and clinical purposes.

By establishing a robust genomics data infrastructure, EGDI aims to accelerate scientific discoveries, facilitate personalised medicine, and enhance collaboration among researchers and institutions within Europe. The infrastructure is expected to provide a foundation for large-scale genomic research projects, foster international collaborations, and contribute to advancements in healthcare and precision medicine.

The Life Science AAI has been identified as a key resource and project product in the GDI StarterKit, providing not just authentication capabilities but also heavy utilisation of the GA4GH interfaces for performing dataset authorisation.

8.2.2 EUCAIM

European Federation for CANcer IMages (EUCAIM) is the cornerstone of the European Commission-initiated European Cancer Imaging Initiative,³¹ a flagship of Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan (EBCP), which aims to foster innovation and deployment of digital technologies in cancer treatment and care to achieve more precise and faster clinical decision making, diagnostics, treatment and predictive medicine for cancer patients.

The project builds upon the results of the work of the “AI for Health Imaging” (AI4HI) Network which consists of 5 large EU-funded projects on big data and Artificial Intelligence in cancer imaging: Chameleon, EuCanImage, ProCancer-I, Incisive and Primage. EUCAIM brings together 76 partners from 14 EU member states, covering competencies in cancer imaging and care, big data in medical imaging, FAIR data management, ethical and legal aspects of medical data, development and deployment of research infrastructures, AI and machine learning, as well as dissemination, communication and stakeholder outreach in biomedical imaging.

In line with the European data strategy and supporting the goals of the European Health Data Space, the EUCAIM will partner with the AI Testing and Experimentation Facility for Health under the Digital Europe Programme, allowing SMEs to access its infrastructure, and rollout will be supported by the services of the European Digital Innovation Hubs. EUCAIM follows an inclusive, collaborative approach and will interact with a plethora of stakeholders to ensure uptake at the political level in member states and wide use of the infrastructure by clinicians, researchers and innovators. Clinical data providers will be invited to join the initiative through an open call procedure during the project.

Life Science AAI is integrated as a login mechanism into the infrastructure with an ongoing discussion of transferring more components of the projects’ existing infrastructure into the Life Science AAI.

³¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cancer-imaging>

8.2.3 EJP-RD

The European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases³² (EJP-RD) is a large-scale research initiative focused on advancing the understanding and treatment of rare diseases. It is a collaborative effort involving numerous research institutions, healthcare organisations, and patient advocacy groups from across Europe.

The main objective of the EJP-RD is to foster collaboration and coordination among stakeholders involved in rare disease research, with the ultimate goal of improving patient outcomes and quality of life for individuals affected by rare diseases.

The project aims to address various challenges associated with rare diseases, including limited knowledge, fragmented research efforts, and difficulties in accessing resources and expertise. By bringing together experts from different disciplines and countries, the EJP-RD project seeks to overcome these challenges and facilitate progress in rare disease research and care.

As in the GDI project, the Life Science AAI has been identified as a key authentication mechanism for entering the Virtual Platform (VP) developed in the project as well as a gateway to authorization of the querying capabilities in the VP Portal. The technical implementation is built around the provisioning of entitlements of a person, recording researcher status, and organisational affiliation and with a vision of adopting the GA4GH standards.

8.2.4 canSERV

canSERV³³ is an EU-funded project under the Horizon Europe programme that provides cutting-edge, interdisciplinary and customised oncology services across the entire cancer continuum. The aim is to offer a comprehensive portfolio of oncology-related research services available to all scientists in EU member countries, associated countries and beyond. The project unites a multidisciplinary consortium of 19 European partners, consisting of Research Infrastructures, key organisations in the field of oncology, project management and sustainability experts.

The primary objective of canSERV is to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of variant interpretation, which involves determining the significance and clinical relevance of genetic alterations identified in cancer patients. By utilising advanced bioinformatics methods and integrating large-scale genomic data, canSERV aims to provide more accurate and standardised interpretations of cancer-related genetic variants.

The canSERV project emphasises collaboration between researchers, clinicians, and other stakeholders to create a comprehensive resource for variant interpretation. It focuses on analysing genomic data from cancer patients to identify potential driver mutations, molecular pathways, and therapeutic targets. This information can help guide personalised treatment decisions and contribute to the development of precision medicine approaches for cancer.

In addition to variant interpretation, the canSERV project may also involve efforts to harmonise data, establish data-sharing protocols, and facilitate collaboration across different research institutions and healthcare settings. By promoting data exchange and standardisation, canSERV aims to accelerate research and improve patient care in the field of cancer genetics.

³² <https://www.ejprarediseases.org/>

³³ <https://www.canserv.eu/>

During the EOSC-Life project, the WP has looked at connecting ARIA with BBMRI Negotiator, a service provided by BBMRI that operates in a similar space but whose services are complementary. The groundwork has now been handed over to the canSERV project for the implementation of integration of these two systems into the ecosystem of Life Science AAI.

8.3 Foreseen challenges

Connecting additional services may bring new technical challenges. However, components used in Life Science AAI are also used in other projects which have very similar architecture to Life Science AAI, and therefore the project is not expecting significant technical problems in future. There is a possibility to organise regular training activities for registering services to Life Science AAI which will help the owners of the services with the registration process and technical integration of their services. The general proposal is to organise such training at least once per year to communicate the updates to the relying services and introduce changes in the registration process.

Another challenge is foreseen in the changing models of working with digital identity, namely the introduction of the Self-Sovereign Identity concept. The Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure will be required to be compatible with such identities as the first step, slowly iterating and following the development process of the concept by adjusting its functionalities to be fully compliant with the concept of decentralised identities and putting the control over the identity into the users' hands.

With the evolution of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), an interesting activity of integrating the Life Science AAI with the other research cluster infrastructures via EOSC AAI is foreseen. One of the challenges in the area is the management of user data processing approvals in an easy-to-grip way, especially with the explosion of services offered to researchers spanning multiple infrastructures and the possibility to confuse what data and where the user's data is located in the multi-infrastructure environment. We need to determine how best to manage this for simplicity and efficiency alongside managing the policy-related activities (GDPR, Acceptable Use Policy, Terms of Use, etc.). Another challenge will be the authorisation in such an environment, where the defined authorisation rules need to be efficiently managed, enforced and possibly shared among the entities playing a role in their enforcement.

Last but not least a huge challenge is foreseen in the area of de-provisioning the data from the different locations when e.g. a user account is going to be deactivated. Due to the nature of the technical protocols deployed to date, this will be a challenging task which will require a great amount of policy work to establish an agreement between the data processing entities. Yet more difficult will be automating such a process.

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Abbreviations

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
ARIA	Access to Research Infrastructure Administration
BMS	Biological and Medical Sciences
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

IAM	Identity and Access Management
ID	Identifier
IdP	Identity Provider
LS	Life Sciences
OIDC	OpenID Connect
RI	Research Infrastructure
SAML	Security Assertion Mark-up Language
SP	Service Provider
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package

Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed:

No delays

Adjustments

Adjustments made:

Updated relevant sections of the D5.2 for the purpose of expressing the end-project state of the art.

Appendices

Appendix A. Life Science AAI policies

- A.1. Acceptable Usage Policy: <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/ls-aai-aup.html>
- A.2. Privacy Notice and Cookie Policy: <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/privacy-notice-for-life-science-login.html>
- A.3. Terms of Use for Relying Parties: <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/terms-of-use-for-service-providers.html>
- A.4. Service Operations security policy: <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/service-operations-security-policy.html>
- A.5. Incident Response Procedures: <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/incident-response-procedures.html>
- A.6. Policy for processing personal data: <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/policy-on-the-processing-of-personal-data-of-the-ls-aai-service.html>

